

“Zero to Hero” in Mindspongeland

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“Sir, what preparation is needed for successful cultivation? – Prepare everything you need, understood? How do I know when I reach the pinnacle of this cultivation? – You will be almost there when you feel dizzy and faint into darkness, then wake up seeing the bright sky. Your trusted people may need to lend their helping wings at that time.”

–In “No-Fish Dietary”; [The Kingfisher Story Collection](#).

[CREDENTIAL]

Are you an Early Career Researcher (ECR) striving for success in academia? If so, I invite you to explore my unconventional path. My journey to success is wandering in mindspongeland with the BMF analytics workhorse [1]. Sounds weird? It is. Sounds unfamiliar? It is. Sounds good? In a strange manner. But unbelievable? Definitely not. I am living proof.

In March 2023, I was introduced to MindSponge Theory (MT) and Bayesian MindSponge Framework (BMF) [2-3] for scientific research. As a healthcare professional and early career researcher (ECR) with a focus on health studies, I decided to venture into social studies using these tools. With the guidance of two mentors initially and two more along the way, I embarked on a 1.5-year journey that significantly shaped my accomplishment in scientific activities. The journey involved three months of rigorous critical appraisal of MT and BMF articles, followed by a year of collaborative BMF studies under a mentor’s supervision and another three months of conducting independent BMF studies. Today, I have the privilege of mentoring others in BMF research.

Throughout this journey, BMF has connected me with a global network of researchers, from

ECRs to Professors Emeritus, spanning from Indonesia to Vietnam and even as far as Africa. Whether in the precise STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields or the complex HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) domains, BMF has proven invaluable in producing high-quality research and publications. This has led me to several international publications in reputable scientific journals [4-6], with more BMF articles currently in the pipeline.

Photo. The girl wandering in the “mindspongeland” (©2024 Courtesy of Wulan)

BMF analytics allow researchers to approach MT with a robust analytical framework supported by the `bayesvl` package built on the R platform [7]. My journey through social studies, utilizing MT and BMF, has incorporated Andrea Lawson’s STEM-for-HASS concept [8]. This interdisciplinary approach has enabled me to mentor other ECRs across diverse scientific fields. Currently, I am mentoring a group of Ph.D. students affiliated with the Faculty of Economic and Management Sciences, School of Public Management and Administration, University of Pretoria, South Africa, in their BMF research endeavors.

So, are you ready to join me on the path to success? I encourage you to delve into MT and BMF as soon as possible.

*Note: As of this publication, the author held a Master's degree in Nursing with nine years of research experience. Mentoring a group of Ph.D. students from various scientific backgrounds marks a significant milestone in her research and publishing journey, thanks to the utilization of MT and BMF.

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